

IMPACT OF TELEVISION PROGRAMME ON POLITICAL AND RELIGIOUS VALUES OF PUPIL TEACHER OF HARYANA

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Abstract

A psychological test of values purports to measure generalized and dominant interest, motive or broad evaluation attitude. Television in India is a huge industry which has thousands of programmes in many languages. The small screen has produced numerous celebrities, some even attaining national fame. More than half of all Indian households own a television. As of 2012, the country has a collection of free and subscription services over a variety of distribution media, through which there are over 823 channels of which 184 are pay channels. Values are not an object or entity of any kind or a personality trait. But it is a non-cognitive or effective characteristic of one's personality. No one is born with values. Values are learnt, developed and are also likely to change in one's life. People acquire experiences they grow and learn. To study the impact of television programme on Political and spiritual values of Pupil Teachers a TELEVISION PROGRAMME VALUE ASSESSMENT SCALE"-MPSA which was developed by Dr. Ajeet Kumar Shankhdhar (Bareilly) and Dr. Pradeep Kumar Misra (Bareilly) was used. Descriptive Survey Method was employed to collect the information. Majority of the pupil teachers accept that television programmes that provide political information contributed in their social development.

Background and Review

In psychology, the term value is used in its specific connotation. Perry (1954) while placing values in the domain of psychology refers to the popular use of the term 'values' which has eclipsed transcendental use by Neo-fitchcon philosophers and its technical use by economists. A set of values may be placed into the nation of a value system. Values are considered subjective and vary across people and cultures. Types of values include ethical/moral values, political, religious value, social value and aesthetic value. The traits characterized under these components are as follows:

- ❖ **Knowledge value:** Attachment with knowledge, education, truth, principle etc.
- ❖ **Economical value:** tendency to collect money means to get money, distinction between right and wrong, etc.
- ❖ **Aesthetic value:** Beauty, drawing, music, dance, acting, literature, love etc.
- ❖ **Social value:** Equality, awareness, social harmony, brotherhood, sympathy help narrowness, social classes etc.

- ❖ **Political value:** Designation, prestige, power, reign, faith in excellence of self, etc.
- ❖ **Religious value:** Existence of power of god, religion, quality detachment with un-religious work etc.
- ❖ **Creative values:** Originality of ideas, tendency, creativity interest towards science and technology etc.
- ❖ **Humanistic value:** Selfless service towards helpless and poor persons, tendency to encourage the self-social status, mercy, emotions etc.

Television in India is a huge industry which has thousands of programmes in many languages. The small screen has produced numerous celebrities, some even attaining national fame. More than half of all Indian households own a television. As of 2012, the country has a collection of free and subscription services over a variety of distribution media, through which there are over 823 channels of which 184 are pay channels. Values are not an object or entity of any kind or a personality trait. But it is a non-cognitive or effective characteristic of one's personality. No one is born with values. Values are learnt, developed and are also likely to change in one's life. People acquire experiences they grow and learn. No teacher in our schools can teach with full effectiveness unless he has a keen understanding of the role of the mass media in the life of his students" (Dale, 1954, p. 8).

Out of experiences may come certain general guides to behaviour, these guides tend to give direction to life and may be called values. Values is a unique concept related to the worth given to specific kinds of object, acts and conditions by individuals and groups. According to report of Secondary Education Commission (1952-53), a system of education should give due weight age to all levels of human experiences-physical, intellectual, emotional, moral, aesthetic and spiritual. It had mentioned that we attach great importance to the role of indirect influence in building up good character.

Several studies have been carried out to investigate 'Impact of media on children and pupil teacher', 'Association of television viewing during childhood with poor educational achievement and 'impact of media on children and adolescent'. But rare studies have been conduct which studied impact of television programme on values of pupil teacher. Keeping in view the importance of values, the investigator has been motivated to study the "Impact of television programme on values of pupil teacher."

Objectives

1. To study the impact of television programme on Political values of Pupil Teachers.
2. To study the impact of television programme on Religious values of Pupil Teachers.

Research Method

Descriptive Survey Method was employed to collect the information. This method is most popular and widely used in the field of social sciences and education as well.

Population

All the Pupil teachers of D.Ed. course in Sonapat district of Haryana constituted the population for the present investigation.

Sample

The sample of the study was selected in 100 Pupil teachers of D.Ed. course in Sonapat districts on random basis.

Tool Used

The investigator used a tool namely "TELEVISION PROGRAMME VALUE ASSESSMENT SCALE"-MPSA which was developed by Dr. Ajeet Kumar Shankhdhar (Bareilly) and Dr. Pradeep Kumar Misra (Bareilly).

Main Findings

- ❖ Majority (55.75 per cent) of the pupil teachers believe that watching of television programmes inspire us to become a politician.
- ❖ Majority (53.75 per cent) of the pupil teachers are in wait for those television programmes which are full of political activities.
- ❖ Majority (53 per cent) of the pupil teachers accept that the contribution of political television programmes in the development of individual personality is more.
- ❖ Some (49.5 per cent) of the pupil teachers liked television artists as they are the owner of attractive personality.
- ❖ Majority (65 per cent) of the pupil teachers indicated if they get the chance to develop a television programme, then they would like to become a director.
- ❖ Majority (55 per cent) of the pupil teachers influenced with the direction of programmes during watching television.
- ❖ Most (71.25 per cent) of the pupil teachers like those educational television programmes which are based on the explanation method.
- ❖ Majority (63.25 per cent) of the pupil teachers liked patriotic musical programme out of musical programmes which are telecasted on television.
- ❖ Majority (51.5 per cent) of the pupil teachers consider that television programmes help us as a citizen in order to create political interest.
- ❖ Majority (53.5 per cent) of the pupil teachers accept that television programmes that provide political information contributed in their social development. Majority (53.5

per cent) of the pupil teachers like to watch those television programmes which deliberate the religious faith.

- ❖ Majority (54.5 per cent) of the pupil teachers like to watch the television programmes which are full of religious belief.
- ❖ Majority (61.5 per cent) of the pupil teachers spends their maximum time in watching cultural programmes on television.
- ❖ Majority (59.5 per cent) of the pupil teachers liked religious channel out of other television channels.
- ❖ Majority (54.5 per cent) of the pupil teachers are in wait for religious television programmes.
- ❖ Majority (59.75 per cent) of the pupil teachers accept that the contribution of religious elaborations programmes on television in the development of individual personality is more.
- ❖ Majority (58 per cent) of the pupil teachers consider if they get opportunity to prepare the television programme then they prefer to make those television programmes which are based on mythological stories.
- ❖ Majority (56.5 per cent) of the pupil teachers liked devotional musical programme out of musical programmes which are telecasted on television.
- ❖ Majority (61 per cent) of the pupil teachers indicate if they disconnected from the entire world then they would like to watch mythical / religious programmes on television.
- ❖ Some (49 per cent) of the pupil teachers like to watch television programmes which are based on mythical culture.
- ❖ Majority (66 per cent) of the pupil teachers accept that religious television programmes significantly contribute in their social development.

Conclusion: While educational technology began as silent films museums, it quickly transitioned to include audiovisual programmes on TV. The teacher is source of all knowledge it will enhance their ability to deliver good values among the coming generations.

References:

- Barron, S.J., Mok, J.J., Land, M. & Kang, T.Y. (1989). You are what you buy: mass mediated judgment of people's worth. *J. Communalization*, 39(2), 46-54. 36.
- Benninga, Jacques S., Berkowitz, Marvin W., Kuehn, Phyllis, and Smith, Karen February 2006, 'Character and Academics: What Good Schools Do', (website), Phi Delta Kappa International, (Vol. 87, No. 6).

- Cantor, J. (1998). "Mommy I am scared": how T.V and movies frighten children and what we can do to protect them. San Diego: Hardcourt.
- Cennamo, K. S. (1993). Learning from video: Factors influencing learner's preconceptions and invested mental effort. Educational Technology Research and Development. Vol. 41(3), p. 33-46.
- Collay, M. (1998). Recherch: Teaching our life histories. Teaching and Teacher Education, Vol. 14(3), p.245-255.
- Das, R.S. (2000). Why education in values? Journal of Value Education. Vol. 1(1), p.31-36.
- Dhankar, N. (2010). Value education. New Delhi: A P H Publishing Corporation.
- Giri, S.V. (2001). Value-based education: concept and practice. Journal of Value Education. Vol.1 (1), p.1-22.
- Kishor, L. (1990). Value oriented education: foundation and frontiers. Delhi: Doaba house.
- Kumar et.al. (2008). Student's awareness of value in the content of secondary level English. Edu.tracks, Hyderabad, vol.7 (8), p.30-31.
- Mathur, S.S (1987). Educational psychology. Agra: Vinod Pushtak Mandir.
- Rao, U. (1999). Values in education. Mumbai: Top publication.
- Setharam, A.R. (2001). Value education content and process. Journal of Value Education. Vol.1 (1), p.23-43.
- Villani, S. (2001); Impact of Media on Children and Adolescent. Journal of the American Academy of child and adolescent psychiatry. Vol.40, p.392-401.